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Influence Of Entrepreneurship Studies On Library And Information Science In Universities In Benue And Nasarawa States

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science in universities in Benue and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. The study investigated two research objectives which were: to determine the influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science curriculum, and to ascertain the benefits of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science undergraduates in universities. The study also had two corresponding research questions and as well tested two hypotheses. The study adopted descriptive research design. Population of the study comprised 2,330 undergraduates of Library and Information Science of Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi (MOAUM), Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi (JOSTUM), Federal University Lafia and Nasarawa State University, Keffi. The study adopted proportionate stratified sampling technique to determine the sample size of 106. A well-structured questionnaire titled: Influence of Entrepreneurship Studies on Library and Information Science Questionnaire (IESLISQ) was the instrument used for data collection. Data collected from the trial-test was analyzed using cronbach alpha correlated coefficient and the instrument yielded alpha coefficient of 0.98. Data collected for the study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while chi-square was used to test research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that entrepreneurship studies has significant influence on Library and Information Science curriculum, and that entrepreneurship studies have significant benefits to Library and Information Science undergraduates. Based on the findings, the study recommended that curriculum developers and university managements should fully incorporate entrepreneurship studies into Library and Information Science curriculum, and that Library and Information Science undergraduates should on their part embrace entrepreneurship studies and be skilled with the needed competencies among others. The study concluded that entrepreneurship studies has come to stay as a game changer and that it should be fully integrated into Library and Information Science curriculum as core course.

Keywords: entrepreneurship studies, Information Science, undergraduates

INTRODUCTION

One of the major issues in the world today is the need to create more jobs. This issue is being compounded every now and then as different fields of study both in the Humanities, Social Sciences,

Management Sciences, Natural and Applied Sciences among others graduate large number of graduates who in their numbers have filled the labour market space. White colour jobs are scarcely available where graduates can be absorbed. As a result of this, so many fields of study have started exploring entrepreneurial opportunities where their students can receive training on how to create wealth in their fields during their studies and after graduation in order to live meaningful lives. In other words, various disciplines of human endeavour have embraced entrepreneurship studies so that their students as undergraduates and even after graduation can stand shoulders high with something to do rather than appearing beggarly. Based on this premise, therefore, entrepreneurship is one critical area in human life that has come to stay. The eyes of so many who are creative are opening on daily basis on how to do old things in new ways. The thought pattern of many people has changed drastically and also widened that they have started thinking outside the box on what ideas can be harnessed to create something new or recreate an old thing in a new way. This is the place and centrality of entrepreneurship in today's world.

In clarity of terms, Babalola (2021) pointed out that entrepreneurship is an individual's ability to manipulate ideas and turn them into reality. Also, Chinemerem (2024) established that entrepreneurship is the activity that involves the discovery, evaluation and exploitation of opportunities within the framework of an individual opportunity nexus. It is looked upon as the activities and processes undertaken to discover, define and exploit opportunities in order to enhance wealth by creating new ventures in an innovative manner. Relatedly, Ekpenyong and Agboke (2021) put it as the movement of an individual or a group of individuals in innovation, risk bearing and organization for the purpose of establishing a venture, managing it to fruition and reaping the resultant benefits. As he succinctly captured, entrepreneurship encompasses creativity, innovation, organization and risk-taking. Creativity in entrepreneurship has to do with invention or discovery of new methods of doing something. Not only this, it has to do with innovation which has to do with utilization of invention and discoveries for the production of new combination. This implies that innovation has to do with value addition to outputs created thereby creating them into marketable products and services.

Another important strand of entrepreneurship is organization which bears on creation and management of a venture. Organization involves the combination of a land of one, labour of another and capital yet another to produce a product. As the product is sold, interest is paid on capital, rent on land, wages on labour and whatever remains is considered as profit. When nothing remains from the sale of a product, risk-taking becomes the next available option. This is when an entrepreneurship combines together products and services and sells them at uncertain prices. This is an indication that merchandise, farming, craftsmanship, librarianship, and other sole proprietorships are entrepreneurs (Ekpenyong and Agboke, 2021).

Entrepreneurship studies therefore is so imperative for Library and Information Science discipline since it has the potentials to enable students especially undergraduates to acquire necessary entrepreneurship skills that will help them fit in and remain relevant in this complex and changing society. This explains why entrepreneurship studies is incorporated into the curricula of so many disciplines. Tondo and Ugba (2023) observed that since institutions of higher learning on yearly basis graduate millions of graduates who are pushed into the labour without corresponding jobs, entrepreneurship studies should be incorporated into Library and Information Science Curriculum to adequately prepare their students (undergraduates) with skills needed for self-reliance, sustainability and survival while in school and after school. Umunadi (2022) attested that the world is witnessing a wave of entrepreneurship happening with millions of people seeking for self-employment and business ownership since the white colour jobs are never to be found. Entrepreneurship is now a key driver of our economy because we are in an entrepreneurial age where entrepreneurs are driving a revolution that is transforming and renewing economies worldwide which Library and Information profession is not exceptional.

Entrepreneurship studies as a matter of necessity is to be incorporated in the Library and Information Science curriculum. With entrepreneurship studies, the undergraduate studies will look at aspects of librarianship such as cataloguing and classification, indexing, abstracting, information brokerage and book reformatting only to mention a few as entrepreneurial opportunities to explore maximally during their study period. According to Babalola (2021), when the training in Library and Information Science is

holistic and really in-debt, undergraduate students will learn, develop and acquire practical skills in all facets of librarianship and begin to practice even before their graduation in order to make fortunes and live sustainable lives.

Entrepreneurship studies hold quite a number of benefits to Library and Information Science undergraduate students. According to Tondo and Ugba (2023), the role of entrepreneurship studies to library and information science students is very essential since entrepreneurship has to do with problem solving using entrepreneurship skills, skill acquisition, self-employment, marketing of Library and Information Science products and services and many more. Entrepreneurship studies would be of great benefits to undergraduates of LIS in ways such as: empowering Library and Information Science undergraduate students to create jobs for themselves while studying in order to be self-reliant and reduce financial burdens on their parents and relations, equipping Library and Information Science students with diversified knowledge and creative abilities to initiate, establish and run businesses that will make them stable, dependable and self-reliant, it provides them additional skills that will empower them to transfer their ideas into visible ventures, promotion of innovations by introducing new products and services as well as market strategies to LIS students to become outstanding entrepreneurs during and after school, it helps to develop innovative skills in potential librarians and information scientists, it goes a long way to bridging the gap between science and the market place by creating new enterprise (Morrison, 2020); it also, prepares LIS undergraduate students with the necessary skills to create and succinctly operate business ventures. Lastly, entrepreneurship studies reposition Library and Information Science undergraduate so that they can succeed and remain relevant in this entrepreneurial economy after graduation.

Having established the above scenario, Departments of Library and Information Science in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi and Federal University, Lafia and Nasarawa State University, Keffi in Benue and Nasarawa States have the duty incumbent on them to fully enshrine entrepreneurship studies into the mainstream of the discipline and adequately train their undergraduate students to be very versatile with all the facets and ramifications of the field. Entrepreneurship studies as a matter of necessity is to be incorporated in the Library and Information Science curriculum. With entrepreneurship studies, the undergraduate studies will look at aspects of librarianship such as cataloguing and classification, indexing, abstracting, information brokerage and book reformatting only to mention a few as entrepreneurial opportunities to explore maximally during their study period and long after graduation and life will be meaningful. It is in consideration of all these that this study focuses on the influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science of Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.

Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurship is the new order that has come to stay. It is the driving force of economies of nations across the world. All fields of study, including Library and Information Science have fully embraced it to tap of its potentialities. In library and information science, entrepreneurship studies has brought about the concept of innovation and newness as integral part of the field. It looks at all aspects of librarianship and all routine functions and services such as cataloguing and classification, indexing, abstracting, information brokerage and book reformatting among others as entrepreneurial opportunities for undergraduates to exploit or effectively harness for their sustainability either for monetary reward, personal satisfaction and independence. With entrepreneurship, old services are repackaged, and through innovativeness produced and offered in new ways.

It is worrisome, however, that entrepreneurship studies is not fully incorporated into Library and Information Science curriculum. Personal investigation reveals that Library and Information Science Departments of Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nasarawa State University, Keffi and Federal University, Lafia of Benue and Nasarawa States seem not to fully embrace entrepreneurship studies as they should thereby leaving their students in the dark on the existing potentialities that in abundance. As a result, the consequence of unemployment, underemployment and joblessness follows these students even after graduation. It is against this background that this study seeks to look at the

influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science of universities in Benue and Nasarawa States-Nigeria.

Purpose of Study

The general purpose of study is to examine the influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States. Specific objectives of the study were to

- i. examine the influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science Curriculum in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.
- ii. ascertain the benefits of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Students of Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.

Research Questions

The study has the following research questions:

- i. What is the influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science Curriculum of Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States?
- ii. What are the benefits of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science Students of universities in Benue and Nasarawa States?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO1. Entrepreneurship studies do not have significant influence on Library and Information Science Curriculum in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.

HO2. Entrepreneurship Studies do not have significant benefits on Library and Information Science Students in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship

The concept of entrepreneurship is variously described. It is also not properly understood by many. According to Ottih (2016), mainly people including some authors on the subject confuse entrepreneurship with any of the concepts: small business, business management, and skills acquisition. These are neither the hub nor the heart of the matter. They pointed out that entrepreneurship refers to the activities and processes of new venture creation and the management of the new venture to a stable state. This definition emphasizes the personality, the process and the enterprise. The new ventures are not limited to business ventures. It can be community development venture, social action venture, church venture, libraries and information organizations as ventures among others. The new venture can therefore be a profit or non-profit venture, although the emphasis of entrepreneurship is on business venture creation. In a conference at Harvard business school in 1984 cited in Ottih (2016), entrepreneurship was defined as an effort to create value through the recognition of business opportunity, the management of risk-taking appropriate to the opportunity and through the communicative and management skills to mobilize human financial and material resources necessary to bring a project to fruition. Robert Histich in Ottih (2016) defined entrepreneurship as the process of creating something different with value by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the financial, psychological and social risk and receiving the resulting rewards of monetary, personal satisfaction and independence. Entrepreneurship, according to Bassey and Adu (2022) is the act of being an individual having the willingness to establish and run an enterprise successfully. It is the process of creating wealth or establishment of business in which individuals can employ themselves for the purpose of making a good living, solving problems and people's needs. In a very succinct way, Omeodu (2019) posits that entrepreneurship is a means of providing employment and income generation in the country and a panacea to poverty reduction and pathetic unemployment situation. It is simply the process of doing new things or amending old things in a new way. According to Zarha, Fakhrisadat and Narge (2014), entrepreneurship is described as the methods of bringing together innovative ideas, management skills and organizational skills to combine both people, money and other resources to satisfy human needs.

More so, Tongo and Ugba (2023) looked at entrepreneurship as the activity that involves the discovery, evaluation and exploitation of opportunities within the framework of an individual opportunity nexus. The duo also considered it as the activities and processes undertaken to discover, define and exploit opportunities in an innovative manner. In their view, the key concepts of entrepreneurship are innovation, market orientation and system change.

Contextually, the researcher looks at entrepreneurship as the involvement of an individual or a group of individuals in innovation, risk-bearing and organization for the purpose of establishing a venture, managing it to fruition and reaping the resultant benefits. It is the process of discovering new ways of combining resources to achieve a set goal.

Entrepreneurship Studies

The Nigerian educational system is in a serious crisis as this paves way for frequent cases of youth restiveness, armed robbery, prostitution, kidnapping and the likes. The cause of these social maladies is traceable to high prevalence of unemployment which is as a result of youths not being given necessary and practical skills that relate to their disciplines while in school. Musa and Tsafe (2019) in their study observed that majority of Nigerian graduates who completed the mandatory national youth service (NYSC) in the last five years are unemployed. The situation portrays failure of the nation's educational system to fully incorporate entrepreneurship studies into the curricular of the various fields of study in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education. All these have necessitated the introduction of entrepreneurship studies into the curricular of all institutions of higher learning in Nigeria by National University Commission (NUC) and National Board for Technical Education (NBTE).

Therefore, there is urgent need to prepare undergraduates, those in Library and Information Science inclusive in the Nigeria's higher institutions for the challenges and benefits of self-employment. This can be achieved, according to Erhirheme and Ekpeyen (2012) only if the concerned stakeholders like the Departments of Library and Information Science in our universities and other institutions, the Librarian Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN), the Nigerian Library Association (NLA) can systematically accommodate entrepreneurship education courses in their curriculum as this will greatly help in the production of sound graduates of library and information science. Furthermore, the advent of information and communication technology in librarianship has open new forms of information packages and packaging thereby, uplifting the frontiers of Library and Information Science profession.

Benefits of Entrepreneurship Studies

The role of entrepreneurship studies in library and information science is very essential such as that entrepreneurship is described in the light of this as solving problems in library and information science profession using entrepreneurship skills. Musa and Tsafe (2019) pointed out that entrepreneurship studies equip the students of library and information science with much needed skills to focus and drive the realization of profit maximization opportunities. After graduation, they can as professionals, acquire entrepreneurial skills through conferences, seminars and workshop attendance as this will expose them to various and numerous business opportunities available in the profession.

The benefits of entrepreneurship studies to Library and Information Science are inexhaustible. Tondo and Ugba (2023) stated the benefits of entrepreneurship are as thus; entrepreneurship studies empower library and information science undergraduates to create jobs for themselves and be self-employed as well as self-reliant; it equips library and information science undergraduates with diversified knowledge and creative abilities to initiate, establish and run businesses that will contribute to national development; provides LIS undergraduates with additional skills that empower them to transform their ideas into visible ventures. Also, entrepreneurship according to Umuradi (2022) promotes innovations by introducing new products and services as well as market strategies to LIS undergraduates to become outstanding entrepreneurs; serving as an effective method of bridging the gap between science and the market place creating new enterprise; it helps to develop innovative skills in potential librarians and information scientists; prepares LIS undergraduates with the necessary skills to create and successfully operate business ventures even as students; lastly, entrepreneurship studies reposition LIS undergraduates so that they can succeed even after graduation and remain relevant in this entrepreneurial economy.

Entrepreneurship studies hold quite a number of benefits to library and information science undergraduates. Olorunfemi and Ipadeola (2018) posited that entrepreneurship studies ensure improvement in the promotion of the use of information resources; with innovation, it creates a new perception of need for information products and services and thereby create demand; also, entrepreneurship helps in ensuring optimum use of information; brings about improvement in the image and status of the libraries and library profession helps in tackling the problems of rising costs of reading materials; journals and databases as librarian entrepreneurs through information brokerage services at the fee moderately better than the real cost of information resources; more so, entrepreneurship introduces to offer such library and information science undergraduates cutting edge information technology system with entrepreneurship, Library and Information Services are provided in the most friendly and cost-effective manner as well upholding the dictum that information is power.

In summary, Musa and Tsafe (2019) made it crystal clear that entrepreneurship studies equip the students of library and information science with much needed skills to focus and drive the realization of profit maximization opportunities. After graduation from the university, they can as professionals acquire entrepreneurial skills through conference, seminar and workshop attendance as this exposes them to the numerous business opportunities available in the profession.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted descriptive research design. The reason for the design was because the study and its variables were descriptive in nature. The area of study was Benue and Nasarawa States. The population of the study comprised of 2,330 undergraduates of Library and Information Science of Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States. The breakdown of the population showed that Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi had 1,033, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi – 174, Federal University, Lafia – 762 and Nasarawa State University, Keffi – 361. The sample size of the study was 117 which was determined using proportionate stratified sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a well structured questionnaire titled: Influence of Entrepreneurship Studies on Library and Information Science Curriculum Questionnaire (IESLISCQ). The instrument was validated by three experts. It was also trial-tested in University of Jos. The choice of University of Jos for the trial-test of the instrument was because it shares the same characteristics with universities in the study area. The trial-test of the instrument yielded the alpha correlated coefficient of 0.96. This indicated that the coefficient was high and reliable enough to be used for the study. Data collected for the study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation while chi-square was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science Curriculum of Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States?*

Table 1: Influence of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science Curriculum in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States

S/N	Option	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	σ	Remark
1.	Makes the teaching of library and information science more practical as it shifts away from reliance of theoretical aspect.	106	55	48	2	1	3.48	0.59	Agree
2.	Infuses entrepreneurial innovation into various aspects of librarianship where things are done in new ways.	106	46	47	8	5	3.26	0.79	Agree
3.	Enriches library and information science curriculum such that all areas of librarianship are taught as entrepreneurial opportunities for students to exploit.	106	43	57	4	2	3.33	0.64	Agree

4.	Makes library and information science curriculum to place emphasis on innovations by way of seeking improvement of productivity and achievement of competitiveness and advantage.	106	40	52	6	8	3.17	0.84	Agree
5.	Helps library and information science curriculum to attach importance on practical aspects of library and information science such as publishing, production and sales of library equipment, information brokerage, photocopying and bindery.	106	45	50	8	3	3.29	0.72	Agree
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation							3.31	0.72	Agree

Source: *Field Survey, 2025*

Table 1 shows the mean scores of items 1-5 as 3.48, 3.26, 3.33, 3.17 and 3.29 with corresponding standard deviations of 0.59, 0.79, 0.64, 0.84 and 0.72 respectively. All the items were above the criterion mean of 2.50. The cluster mean of 3.31 with corresponding standard deviation of 0.72 was high above the criterion mean of 2.50. This means that entrepreneurship studies makes the teaching of library and Information science more practical, infuses entrepreneurial innovations into various aspects of librarianship, enriches library and information science curriculum, makes Library and Information Science curriculum to place emphasis on innovations and creativity, and helps library and Information Science curriculum to attach importance on the practical aspects of library and information science. This implies that entrepreneurship studies significantly influences Library and Information Science curriculum in universities in Benue and Nasarawa States

Table 2: Benefits of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science Undergraduates in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States

S/N	Option	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	σ	Remark
1.	Helps in job creation and to be self-reliant.	106	53	42	9	2	3.38	0.72	Agree
2.	Equips them with diverse skills and creative abilities.	106	49	42	5	10	3.23	0.92	Agree
3.	Promotes innovations by introducing new products and services.	106	38	52	7	9	3.12	0.87	Agree
4.	Provides additional skills to transform ideas into visible ventures.	106	33	49	15	9	3.00	0.89	Agree
5.	Repositions undergraduates to succeed and remain relevant during and after study.	106	41	59	2	4	3.29	0.69	Agree
6.	Prepares undergraduates with the necessary skills to create and successfully operate business ventures.	106	40	50	7	9	3.14	0.88	Agree
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation							3.19	0.83	Agree

Source: *Field Survey, 2025*

Table 2 shows the mean scores of items 1-6 as 3.38, 3.23, 3.12, 3.00, 3.29 and 3.14 with corresponding standard deviations of 0.72, 0.92, 0.87, 0.89, 0.69 and 0.88 respectively. All the items were above the criterion mean of 2.50. The cluster mean score of 3.19 with corresponding standard deviation of 0.83 was

high above the criterion mean of 2.50. This means that entrepreneurship studies is of benefits to Library and Information Science undergraduates since it helps in job creation and to be self-reliant, equipping them with diverse skills and creative abilities, promoting innovation by introducing new products and services, providing additional skills to transform ideas into tangible ventures, repositioning undergraduates to succeed and remain relevant, and preparing undergraduates with the necessary skills to successfully operate business ventures. By implication, entrepreneurship studies was of significant benefits to Library and Information Science undergraduates in Benue and Nasarawa States.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Entrepreneurship studies do not have significant influence on Library and Information Science Curriculum in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.

Table 3: Chi-Square (χ^2) test of influence of entrepreneurship studies on library and information science curriculum in universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.

	Level of Sig.	df	χ^2_{cal}	P-Value	Decision
Influence of entrepreneurship studies on library and information science curriculum in universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.	0.05	14	331.264 ^a	0.000	Sig.

Table 3 is a chi-square evaluation of the influence of entrepreneurship studies on the Library and Information Science (LIS) curriculum in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States. With a level of significance set at 0.05, the computed Chi-Square value ($\chi^2_{cal} = 331.264$, $df = 14$) was substantially higher than the critical value for the given degrees of freedom, and the associated p-value of 0.000 was well below the 0.05 threshold. This indicates that the relationship between the inclusion of entrepreneurship studies and the LIS curriculum is statistically significant, meaning the observed influence is unlikely to have occurred by chance. The significant result implies that entrepreneurship studies play a notable role in shaping or impacting the structure, content, or orientation of the LIS curriculum in the studied universities. Consequently, it can be inferred that integrating entrepreneurship into LIS programmes is not only relevant but may also contribute to equipping graduates with entrepreneurial skills and competencies that enhance employability and self-reliance in a dynamic information and job market environment.

H₀₂: Entrepreneurship studies do not have significant benefits on Library and Information Science Undergraduates in Universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.

Table 4: Chi-Square (χ^2) test of benefits of entrepreneurship studies on library and information science undergraduates in universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.

	Level of Sig.	df	χ^2_{cal}	P-Value	Decision
Benefits of Entrepreneurship studies on library and information science undergraduates in universities in Benue and Nasarawa States.	0.05	15	217.623 ^a	0.000	Sig.

Table 4 is a chi-square assessment of the benefits of entrepreneurship studies on Library and Information Science undergraduates in universities within Benue and Nasarawa States. At a 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) and 15 degrees of freedom, the calculated Chi-Square value ($\chi^2_{cal} = 217.623$) was substantially higher than the critical Chi-Square value for the given degrees of freedom, indicating a strong deviation from the null hypothesis of no significant association. The corresponding p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) confirms that the observed differences are statistically significant. This implies that respondents overwhelmingly consider entrepreneurship studies as having notable benefits for Library and Information Science undergraduates, suggesting that entrepreneurship studies plays a vital role in equipping students with practical skills and fostering self-reliance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it's affirmed that entrepreneurship education significantly benefits students in the studied population.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the analysis of the research questions and hypotheses, the following findings have been discussed.

The first finding of the study revealed that entrepreneurship studies positively influences Library and Information Science curriculum as it makes the teaching of the course more practical, infuses entrepreneurial innovations into various aspects of librarianship, enriches LIS curriculum by teaching entrepreneurial opportunities for students to exploit, makes LIS curriculum to emphasize on innovations as well as helping LIS curriculum to attach importance on practical. This finding was in collaboration with that of Bassey and Adu (2023) which found out that incorporating entrepreneurship into Library and Information Science curriculum equips Library and Information Science graduates with diversified knowledge and creative abilities to initiate, establish and run business that will contribute to national development.

The second finding of the study revealed the benefits of entrepreneurship studies to Library and Information Science undergraduates which included helping in job creation and to be self-reliant, equipping them with diverse skills and creative abilities, promoting innovations by introducing new products and services, providing additional skills to transform ideas into visible ventures, repositioning undergraduates to succeed and remain relevant during and after study, and preparing undergraduates with the necessary skills to create and successfully run business ventures. This finding agreed with that of Tondo and Ugba (2023) which found that entrepreneurship education plays a vital role in Library and Information Science graduates' employability and supports economic development. The finding also collaborated with that of Musa and Tsafe (2019) which revealed that entrepreneurship studies plays the role of alleviating societal and economic problems such as unemployment, economic recession, poverty and youth restiveness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher drew conclusion that entrepreneurship has come to stay and has taken its pride of place, especially now that white-colour jobs are not easy to come by. The entrepreneurship studies is to be fully embraced and incorporated into Library and Information Science curriculum to be undertaken by the undergraduate students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. That entrepreneurship studies be fully incorporated into Library and Information Science curriculum by curriculum developers where emphasis will be placed on practical more than theoretical aspect so that the impact of it will be seriously felt. Teachers should be equipped with all the skills needed to effectively deliver.
2. That since entrepreneurship studies tremendously benefit Library and Information Science undergraduates, it should be deeply entrenched into the very life of the course. Curriculum developers should make entrepreneurship studies to be seen as the life wire for Library and Information science to be taught as core course and not as an optional one.

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